

Envisioning the Era of 3D Printing in the Textile and Fashion Industry

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Abstract:

The widespread potential of 3D printing technology has led to it being heralded as a major innovation of the so-called "fourth industrial revolution." Dramatic inventions have been noticed in the last few years in the fashion sector too making use of 3D/ 4D printing. The use of 3D printing in the fashion industry yields excellent outcomes. However, there is a robust connection between the worlds of fashion and 3D printing, and incredible new projects are being revealed on a daily basis. With 3DP, designers and consumers alike can make goods that are both unique and intricate. Designers and manufacturers of clothes have recently come to recognize the significance and benefits of 3D printing technology, which has led to a rise in the use of 3D printers in the textile and fashion industries. Significant curiosity has been sparked, and it appears to have considerable potential for fashion design goods. In this paper, we sought to update a previous evaluation of 3DP technology in the fashion sector to reflect the most up-to-date findings. In this study, the author has covers the review of 3D printing material, the printing process, use of different 3D software, and summarized the advantages and limitations of 3DP in comparison to the traditional manufacturing process. Furthermore, examples of how 3D printing has been used in the fashion industry are provided.

Graphical Abstract

Keywords: 3D Printing, 3D Software, Envisioning, Industry, Manufacturing Process

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1. Introduction

Using digital design tools like CAD, CAM, or other electronic design tools, 3D printing (also known as additive manufacturing, or AM) rapidly and efficiently produces 3D objects layer by layer [1]. Compared to more conventional printing technologies, 3DP can produce extensive 3D structures in a shorter time frame and at a lower cost [2]. The 3DP method involves the gradual deposition of material (much like a coating) in order to construct an object [3]. Decoration of the fabric's surface can be done with no adhesives when three-dimensional printing is used on textile substrates [4]. While chemical bonding is certainly a part of the attachment of 3DP materials to textiles [5], revealed that the key factor was the real-world "locking" of textiles and printing supplies. Although 3DP can be printed on a variety of materials, controlling its adherence, durability, and stability has proven challenging so far [5]. Furthermore, 3DP has received a lot of interest in the textile and fashion industries in recent years due to its adaptability in terms of size and shape. Unlike the fabrication of conventional textiles, 3DP technology enables the creation of very complex structures and permits personalized customization according to the wearer's body via 3D scanning [6]. Due to raw material constraints, however, it is challenging to manufacture goods with the same flexibility, scalability, and pore structure as conventional textiles; a lot of people are interested in the idea of using 3D printing to create textiles with practical applications these days.

Since Chuck Hull, co-founder of 3D Systems, created the first 3D printer in 1983 [7], there have been significant advancements in additive manufacturing technology. The ability of 3D printing technology to rapidly and accurately produce complicated structures has increased its popularity in recent years. Furthermore, cutting-edge technologies like bioprinting and 4D printing have expanded medical practice's potential [8]. Development in additive manufacturing has reached a pinnacle, making it possible to 3D print with a wide variety of materials, including metals, thermoplastics, hydrogels, extracellular matrix materials, ceramics, fiber-reinforced composites, polymers, concrete materials, and even shape memory alloys & polymers and variety of other smart materials [9]. The fashion industry is also going through the industrial revolution from design to production. The use of computers and other digital technologies to design and create products is known as "digital manufacturing," and it has progressed significantly over the years. The environment created by the Fourth Industrial Revolution is one in which virtual and physical production systems work with one another on a global scale in a highly adaptable fashion. One of the foundations of Industry 4.0 is the incorporation of digital manufacturing, which has been shown to decrease production time, costs, and errors while increasing production efficiency and product quality. In addition to the industry's interest, consumers have a lot riding on the fashion industry's transition to digital.

2. 3D Printing in the Fashion and Textile Industries

a) Fashion Design

Designers have been able to produce a wide range of inventive and intricate clothing that would be hard to produce using more conventional textile manufacturing techniques due to the flexibility provided by 3D printing. For instance, Nervous System Studio [10] used SLS printing nylon to make a petal dress with over 1600 individual components and over 2600 hinges. Inspired by the intricate patterns found on the wings of minuscule butterflies, artist Julia Koerner worked with STRATASYS to experiment with digital pattern design and multi-color 3D printing on cloth. Following this, the butterfly design was 3D-printed directly onto the stretchy fabric without the use of a support structure [11]. They created the "ARID collection," which consisted of 38 separate 3D-printed pieces that could be put together to form a garment. The designers made a point of using 3D-printed joinery for all seams so that no sewing was required at any point in the process [12]. The 3D printing technology allowed Acne Studios to create a bag for the 2019 fall/winter season [13]. Using a 3D printer and TPU filament, Nike [14] created the Nike Flyprint upper. When compared to conventional 2D materials, 3D uppers have improved pliability, weight, and breathability by connecting the warp and weft in new ways.

b) Functional Garments

Another exciting area of study is the application of 3D printing technology to the production of functional clothing. This is possible because the technology may be used to generate fibers or fabric with a unique textile structure or by adding functional components. By combining poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA) and boron nitride (BN) in a 3D printer [15] were able to create a thermally conductive fiber with improved thermal transport capabilities of textiles for individual cooling. Additionally [16] developed a 3D-printed thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) mesh fabric with digitally adjusted mechanical characteristics and shape [17] used SLS technology to create a structured fabric with

a progressive transition between soft and hard states, with the granular particles in its two layers interlocking with one another.

c) Electronic Textiles

These technologies are widely used in the field of e-textiles because they can swiftly and accurately print intricate functional structures using 3DP [18]. One example is the fabrication, by ink printing with a coaxial spinneret, of a textile substrate bearing a core-sheath fiber-based smart design [19]. Stretchable elastic fibers and smart textiles with a coaxial core-sheath structure using 3DP technology were also developed [20], with graphene serving as the conductive core and PTFE serving as the insulative sheath. Triboelectric nanogenerators (TEGs) were developed [21] using 3D printing to create a three-dimensional, hierarchically porous structure; the TEGs were made from a matrix of poly (glycerol sebacate) (PGS) and electrodes of conductive carbon nanotubes (CNTs).

d) Materials used in 3D printing

Material plays a crucial role in the realm of 3D printing because it influences how the art of 3D Fashion is created and serves as the basis for new developments in 3D printing technology. A multitude of materials, each with special qualities and features, can be utilized to 3D print fashion apparel. Here are some materials that are frequently used in 3D printing for clothing.

e) Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU)

TPU is a flexible, elastic substance that is frequently used in 3D printing for apparel. It is ideal for uses like sportswear, activewear, and lingerie because of its outstanding stretchability, toughness, and comfort.

f) Polyamide (Nylon)

Nylon, often known as polyamide, is a versatile material used in 3D printing for apparel. It is renowned for its fortitude, adaptability, and strength. The smooth and fabric-like texture of nylon prints makes them ideal for creating clothing with complicated patterns and challenging geometries.

g) Thermoplastic Elastomer (TPE)

TPE is a flexible, rubber-like substance that is frequently used in 3D printing for accessories for clothing, such as shoes, belts, and jewelry. It enables the development of pleasant and useful fashion products by offering flexibility, impact resistance, and high elasticity.

h) Polyester

Polyester is a synthetic fabric that is frequently used in the fashion industry and may also be utilized as a 3D printing material. Polyester prints are appropriate for a variety of garment applications because they can provide good strength, durability, and colour vibrancy.

i) Polyethylene Terephthalate Glycol (PETG)

PETG, a translucent and strong material, is frequently used in 3D printing to create jewellery, accessories, and other decorative items. It offers strong chemical resistance, impact resistance, and printing simplicity.

j) Thermoplastic Polyurethane Elastomer (TPU-E)

TPU-E is a specific thermoplastic elastomer that combines flexibility, elasticity, and toughness. It is made of polyurethane. Stretchable and form-fitting clothing, such as swimwear, activewear, and compression apparel, are created using in 3D printing.

k) Conductive Materials

Conductive materials, such as conductive filaments or inks, are used in 3D printing to create garments with integrated electronic components or sensors. These materials enable the production of smart clothing with capabilities like sensing, heating, or lighting.

l) Bio-based and Sustainable Materials

With a growing emphasis on sustainability in the fashion industry, bio-based and sustainable materials are gaining popularity in 3D printing. Filaments made from PLA (Polylactic Acid) or PHA (Polyhydroxyalkanoates) are examples of biodegradable and compostable materials. Materials for 3D printing currently consist mostly of novel polymers, resin materials, metals, and composites. The specifics are outlined below.

Figure 1 - Different materials are used in 3D printing for the Fashion Industry

3. Mechanism of 3D/4D Printing

Pre-processing is the first step in the 3D printing process. During this stage, the model is created using computer-aided design (CAD) programs like AutoCAD, Rhino, 3Ds Max, etc. The model is then told to be sliced horizontally into x and y layers by the software. In order to print the layers at their specified locations, the CAD-controlled digital file communicates with the printer [22]. The information and commands are then transferred to the CAM system, which constructs the final form of the object. Sanding, polishing, and painting the result, as well as trimming off any excess material, all fall under the "final phase" [23]. Replicating the fabric's pattern exactly necessitates a very high resolution, hence the resolution needed to create textile structure is extremely small and precise [22, 24]. Filaments for 3DP are often made from Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS), Poly Lactic Acid (PLA), or Poly Vinyl Alcohol (PVA). Technologies such as stereolithography (SLA), selective laser sintering (SLS), inkjet printing, binder jetting, and fused deposition modelling (FDM) are utilized to create 3D textiles and fashion accessories [22], [23]. Ultraviolet (UV) lasers are used in stereolithography to harden successive layers of photopolymer resin, a liquid plastic, used in the creation of three-dimensional objects [4]. Objects can be printed from a wide variety of powdered materials, including polymers, metals, ceramics, and composites, using a process called selective laser sintering [25]. Fused deposition modelling involves the layer-by-layer extrusion of molten thermoplastic filament from a nozzle onto a printing bed in the form of a wire-shaped, thin production-grade filament [26].

3D printing using glue or binder bonding agents to fuse powder ingredients and then create consecutive layers of powder materials to build the 3D printed goods is called "binder jetting" [22]. The ink droplet in inkjet printing is propelled out of a microscopic aperture in the printing head by heating the liquid ink, causing bubbles to develop in the ink reservoir [27].

Figure 2 - Steps of 3D printing

4. 3D printing process methods and design & modelling software

Table.1 displays the characteristics of the three most used traditional 3D printing processes: fused deposition modelling (FDM), selective laser sintering (SLS), and stereolithography (SLA).

According to the underlying forming principle of each 3D printing technology, a unique set of materials can be used for printing. To create a solid object, a fused deposition model (FDM) printer melts filaments of thermoplastic material and extrudes the molten material via a nozzle. The filamentary hot-melt materials most commonly

employed in the Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) process have the advantages of a wide variety of forming materials and high strength of produced parts at the expense of low processing accuracy and a rather rough surface. This technique is widely used in today's 3D printing items. One of the raw materials utilised in FDM technology is PLA, which was used to print the clothing displayed at the Asian art museum in San Francisco. Therefore, fused deposition modelling (FDM) was previously the most popular approach to 3D printing [28]. Using a lamination technique for particle sintering, the selective laser sintering (SLS) process builds 3D printed objects by repeatedly irradiating and sintered powder or particles applied to a machine tool. Powders and tiny particles are commonly used in SLS. The crystallisation collection suit by Iris Van Herpen and Daniel Widrig, for instance, is made from polyamide. This approach has the benefits of a straightforward production procedure in addition to a large selection of inexpensive printing raw materials, a high forming speed, and a low material cost. The printer, while effective, is both cumbersome and costly.

In the realm of 3D printing, SLA technology is a mainstay. The liquid resin is deposited in a reservoir, and a programmable laser is scanned over its surface to commence photopolymerization, so completing the photo-hardening process. Chemical crosslinking is the mechanism through which the resin typically solidifies and becomes inflexible after having been a liquid [29]. Iris Van Herpen's Hybrid Holism collection, for instance, was the inspiration for a see-through dress.

At the meso- and micro-scales, Direct-Ink-Writing (DIW) is a popular additive manufacturing technique that relies on extrusion to deposit ink. The DIW process involves layer-by-layer fabrication of 3D structures by dispensing liquid-phase "ink" from small nozzles at controlled flow rates and depositing it along digitally determined routes. 3D printing using inkjet lamination (also known as 3DP). The process involves spraying the raw powder with colored ink and a liquid solidified component through a nozzle [30].

Table 1. Analysis of various process methods

S. No.	Process method	Main materials	Medium	Advantages	Disadvantages	References
1	FDM	ABS plastic PLA plastic	Solid	1. cheap price 2. High utilization 1. Strong support 2. Not easy to deform	1. The surface is rough and requires a framework. Low adaptability; only one texture available	[31]
2	SLS	Plastic powder	Power	1. High processing accuracy 2. No support needed	rough surface	[32]
3	SLA	Photosensitive resin material	Liquid	1. Fast forming speed 2. Smooth surface	Expensive	[33]
4	EHID	PP, PLA, PCL	Solid/liquid	Reasonably priced, user-friendly, flexible, and nanofiber-based	Low mechanical quality, sluggish construction times	[34]
5	DIW	Polymers, waxes, ceramics	Liquid	Quick processing times, no filler required	Material constraints	[34,35]
6	Inkjet	PLA, PCL, poly (lactide co-glycolide)	Liquid	Design complex structures	Slow build speeds, material limitation	[35]

		(PLGA), ceramics				
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The fashion industry utilizes various software tools for 3D printing to enable the design, optimization, and production of fashion garments and accessories. Here are some of the commonly used software in the 3D printing process within the fashion industry:

Figure 3. 3D printing Software

In 3D printing of fashion clothing, various software tools are used to create and prepare 3D models for printing. These software tools enable designers to visualize their designs, optimize them for 3D printing, and generate the necessary files for the printing process. The majorly used 3D printing software in fashion industry are Grasshopper for Rhino, OpenSCAD, Onshape FreeCAD, and Fusion 360 (with parametric design capabilities). Table 2. Can be referred for the analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of materials used in additive manufacturing.

Table 2: Analysis of Advantages and Disadvantages of Materials [36]

S. No.	Material Name	Advantages	Disadvantages	References
1	ABS plastic	1. Consistent physical properties and high resistance to wear 2. The colors don't fade easily	1. The optimal temperature range for the platform is between 80 and 120 degrees Celsius. 2. Large-scale production on a mass scale is not simple.	[36]
2	ALS Nylon powder Material	1. High resilience to both heat and wear 2. Very strong tensile properties	1. Reduced sensitivity to colour. 2. Extreme heat is used in manufacturing.	[37]
3	Photosensitive resin	1. High tensile strength and rapid curing time 2. Finished garments have a sleek finish that is well-suited for individualized designs.	1. Poor heat and wear resistance	[38]

		3. A lot of resources are reused and recycled		
4	Rubber materials	1. Excellent durability and pliability 2. Sufficient adaptability and high levels of comfort	1. Poor environmental safeguards and a low rate of reuse	[39]

5. **3D Printing over conventional methods:** The conventional methods used in fashion industry are giving limited results in terms of accuracy, design constraints, customised designs and productivity. Refer Table. 3 for the major advantages of using 3D printing over the conventional methods.

Table 3. Advantages of using 3D Printing over conventional methods [40,41,42]

Parameters	3D/4D Printing	Conventional method
Flexible Design	When compared to conventional manufacturing techniques, 3D printing facilitates the development and fabrication of more intricate designs. The use of 3D printing eliminates the need to work around the design limitations of more conventional methods.	Production of the complex design is the limitation of the conventional method. Fabrication methods are not very flexible for complex designs.
Rapid Prototyping	With 3DP, parts can be produced in a matter of hours, speeding up the prototyping process and making it simple to change designs. <hr/> In many cases, a 3D-printed component can be ready for use in as little as two hours, making it a more economical and time-efficient option than machining a prototype. Because of this, it takes significantly less time to implement each design change.	Rapid prototyping before 3D printing was expensive and time-consuming.
Restricted Build Size	Despite printing the object in separate pieces because of the restricted build size platform, 3D printing still gives efficient products.	From conventional methods steps of making the separate parts get eliminated and size is not the restriction for making products.
Print on Demand	In 3DP, storing merchandise does not necessitate a sizable warehouse.	Adequate space is required after making the inventory.
Post-Processing	Cleaning up the support material and getting a smooth surface is usually required after 3D printing.	No post-processing is required.
Minimizing Waste	There is no material waste in 3DP manufacturing because just the materials necessary for the part's fabrication are used.	The majority of conventional methods produce waste in some form almost at every stage of production.
Cost-Effective	Inexpensive when mass-produced. Three-dimensional printing (3DP) eliminates the need for several equipment, reducing both production time and costs.	Conventional methods are not very cost-effective.
Advanced Healthcare	Using 3D printing technology, doctors are able to create human parts including livers, kidneys, and hearts to help save patients' lives.	Although many methods are used to make the fashion products used in the healthcare industry.

Copyright Issues	There is a rising risk of fake and counterfeit goods as 3DP becomes more widely available to the general public.	No such issues are there while using conventional methods.
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Table 4. A brief analysis of cases/applications of 3d printing technology in the fashion industry

S. No.	Year	Designer	Product Category	Description	Reference
1	2021	Danit Peleg	Apparel	This lace-like texture was made possible by merging traditional textile features with modern technologies, which influenced the structure of his designs. The outfits are created in layers using desktop 3D printers and a flexible filament.	[43]
2	2022	Iris van Herpen	Apparel/ haute couture dress	The outfit was 3D printed using a vegan organic material derived from cocoa bean shells.	[44]
3	2022	Galerie Dior	garments, handbags, or even shoes	Everything in the manufacturing process is made from renewable sources.	[45]
4	2021	Ronen Samuel-Kornit Digital	Knitwear	Direct-to-yarn printing, which can be done on any type of textile, is one method that Ronen employs in its pursuit of eco-friendly and waste-free clothing. With MAX technology, the ink is added one layer at a time. The product is an item of clothing that mimics the appearance of hand-knitted items. Designs by Ronen Samuel have been shown at the Tel Aviv Fashion Show.	[46]
6	2017	Julia Daviy	fashion, jewelry, and home décor	Eco-Friendly Skirt. This item is the crown jewel of a 3D printed collection that debuted in 2019. Every single garment in the After Forever Collection was printed using a huge 3D printer. Digitally modifiable in over a thousand variations, the Organic Skirt was the first item of apparel to be 3D-printed and sold in the United States.	[47]
7	2022	Stratasys (SSYS 2Y22 Reflection collection)	accessories and apparel	Luxury 3D-printed clothing and accessories from the Reflection collection.	[48]
8	2014	Anouk Wipprecht	Proximity Dress	Multiple sensors built within the clothing may be able to detect nearby motion. In response to a person approaching too closely, the dress can extend to form an obstruction.	[49]
9	2015	Karl Lagerfield	Garments	Karl Lagerfield was one of the first high-end designers to embrace 3D printing. The highly acclaimed designer stunned the Paris Fashion Week crowds with a collection of	[50]

				garments made entirely with 3D software.	
10	2013	Julia Körner	Garment	In the blockbuster film Black Panther, Julia, a prominent fashion designer, is known for her 3D printed garments. She created some spectacular graphics in the form of 3D clothes after developing the first 3D printed outfit in 2013. It appears that JK Design's creator finds most of his inspiration in the natural world.	[50]
11	2019	Zac Posen	Rose Petal Dress	Modeled after a rose, this dress consists of 37 printed petals attached to a frame. The dress was printed using SLA and EBM 3D printing processes.	[51]
12	2018	Maria Alejandra Mora Sanchez	Loom Dress	Inspired by Wayuu, an indigenous tribe in northern Colombia, Sanchez designed the dress to be evocative of the tribe's well-known patterns and textiles. The dress was printed in TPU on an FDM 3D printer.	
13	2016	Danit Peleg	Paralympics Dress	This dress was fitted to Purdy using 3D scanning technology, 3D modeled using Blender, and printed over the course of 100 hours in Recreus' FilaFlex material.	
14	2015	Laura Thapthimkuna	Vortex Dress	This design was modeled with ZBrush and Maya, then printed in Mammoth Resin on an SLA printer.	
15	2015	Anouk Wipprecht	The Spider Dress	Wipprecht's creation was printed on an SLS 3D printer and also incorporates sensors and microcontrollers (Edison chip) to achieve robotic effects.	
16	2014	Kaat Debo, Alexandra Verschueren, and Tobias Klein	Incunabula dress	3D scanning and mesh modeling with 3ds Max were used during the design process. The final dress was printed in polyamide on an SLS 3D printer.	
17	2014	Nervous System	Kinematic Dress	The design was printed as a single print in nylon on an SLS 3D printer. To print the dress in one piece, it was folded up during printing with the hinged triangle panels pre-connected.	
18	2013	Melinda Looi	Gems of the Oceans collection	The dress was modeled with SolidWorks and Magics, then printed in polyamide on an SLS 3D printer in one piece.	

19	2011	Iris Van Herpen	Skeleton Dress	The dress was printed in polyamide using Materialise's laser sintering process.
20	2017	Amirbeygi	Hex Dress	The dress uses a chain mail structure, whose exterior part should be printed face down and with a 0.2-mm layer height according to the original maker.

6. Discussion

The implementation of technology that allows for three-dimensional printing in the apparel and textile industries is advancing at a breakneck speed. The technology of 3D printing may one day completely change the planet. The production of goods and products all over the world could undergo a radical transformation that is both an improvement and a substantial change as a result of developments in 3D printing technology. The development of ideas is accelerated by 3D printing. The ability to print a concept on the same day that it was conceived shortens a development process from what would have been months to what might be a number of days, assisting businesses in remaining one step ahead of their competitors. The recent explosion of interest in digital art and design has given rise to a proliferation of opportunities that are not only rapidly expanding but also virtually unbounded. It is now possible to print almost anything in three dimensions after first sketching it up virtually or in some other way. Artists and research scholars are putting an emphasis on the mix of ease, originality, and innovation of clothes and fabrics, which enables them to create highly complex goods that are also soft and flexible. Nevertheless, the latest developments in 3D printing technology are restricted by size limitations. When it comes to building very huge objects, 3D printers still fall short of expectations. At this point in time, 3D printers are capable of working with around one hundred unique raw materials. This is negligible when weighed against the large variety of raw materials utilized in conventional production.

7. Conclusion

The manufacturing industry is undergoing a radical transformation as a result of the unprecedented growth of 3D printing technology. This flexible approach offers the benefits of customization, prototyping, a variety of production techniques, and complicated geometries in a short amount of time at a low cost. The fashion sector needs to find a new approach and start the necessary programmes to help producers, vendors, businessmen, creators, and customers receive training and education so as to adapt and shift in an expedient and effective way. This study has brought up a conversation about the changes that are expected in the 3DP era. Clearly, the contemporary fashion industry in its entirety continues to go through a transformation and embrace of ongoing technological advances, such as programmes that allow for two-dimensional computerised pattern drafting and virtual reality in fit analysis. To lay the framework for a comprehensive revolution, the industry must make incremental advances and seek niche applications while technological advancements continue. As a result, it is imperative that the fashion sectors remain receptive to the idea of restructuring and reassessing their current knowledge in light of the vocational and learning systems, the multidisciplinary strategy to accomplishing goals in a range of fields, and the information sharing between both sectors in order to facilitate an effective transition.

8. Future Scope

Additional study is required to develop procedures that will make things that have been manufactured with a 3D printer more resilient and long-lasting. Therefore, it is suggested that 3D printing become an official academic discipline, that subsequent works be proposed for improving the conceivable effects of 3D printing, and that the area of study be broadened to encompass all of the building projects accomplished by 3D printing, a variety of substances utilized by 3D printing, and supplemental modeling for multifaceted design procedures.

9. Authors' Contributions

Conceptualization, A.D., A.T., and N.A.; methodology, A.T., A.D.; Framework, A.D, A.T and N.A. Graphics Design, A.T., Literature, A.T., A.D., and N.A.; writing—original draft preparation, A.T, and A.D; writing—review and editing, A.T., A.D., N.A. authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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References:

- [1] MacDonald E, Wicker R. Multiprocess 3D printing for increasing component functionality. *Science*. 2016 Sep 30; 353 (6307): aaf2093. DOI: 10.1126/ science.aaf2093
- [2] Wang BZ, Chen Y. The effect of 3D printing technology on the future fashion design and manufacturing. *Applied Mechanics and Materials*. 2014 Apr 16; 496:2687-91
<https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMM.496-500.2687>
- [3] Vanderploeg A, Lee SE, Mamp M. The application of 3D printing technology in the fashion industry. *International Journal of Fashion Design, Technology and Education*. 2017 May 4; 10 (2):170-9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17543266.2016.1223355>
- [4] Chatterjee K, Ghosh TK. 3D printing of textiles: potential roadmap to printing with fibers. *Advanced Materials*. 2020 Jan; 32 (4):1902086. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201902086>
- [5] Grimmelmann N, Kreuziger M, Korger M, Meissner H, Ehrmann A. Adhesion of 3D printed material on textile substrates. *Rapid Prototyping Journal*. 2018 Jan 2; 24 (1):166-70. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RPJ-05-2016-0086>
- [6] Cabigiosu A, Cabigiosu A. Additive Manufacturing and Smart Textiles. *Digitalization in the Luxury Fashion Industry: Strategic Branding for Millennial Consumers*. 2020:133-71. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-48810-9_6
- [7] Jakus AE. An introduction to 3D printing—past, present, and future promise. In *3D printing in orthopaedic surgery 2019* Jan 1 (pp. 1-15). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-58118-9.00001-4>
- [8] Deshmukh K, Houkan MT, AlMaadeed MA, Sadasivuni KK. Introduction to 3D and 4D printing technology: State of the art and recent trends. *3D and 4D printing of polymer nanocomposite materials*. 2020 Jan 1:1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-816805-9.00001-6>
- [9] Kabir SF, Mathur K, Seyam AF. A critical review on 3D printed continuous fiber-reinforced composites: History, mechanism, materials and properties. *Composite Structures*. 2020 Jan 15; 232:111476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2019.111476>
- [10] Kinematic Petals Dress. Nervous system. Available online: <https://n-e-r-v-o-u-s.com/projects/albums/kinematic-petals-dress/content/kinematic-petals-dress-14/> (accessed on 15 December 2021)
- [11] Julia Korner. Design for Different Futures. JK Design GmbH 2019. Available online: <https://www.juliakoerner.com/setae> (accessed on 15 December 2021)
- [12] Julia Koerner, Architecture's Queen of 3D Fabrication. Available online: <https://www.juliakoerner.com/aridcollection/> (accessed on 15 December 2021)
- [13] Acne studios collaborates with vojfd for 3d fanny pack cases for autumn/winter 2019. OJD Studios. Available online: <https://www.vojdstudios.com/acne> (accessed on 15 December 2021)
- [14] Nike Inc. Newsroom. Available online: <https://news.nike.com/news/eliud-kipchoge-3d-printed-nike-zoom-vaporfly-elite-flyprint> (accessed on 15 December 2021)
- [15] Gao T, Yang Z, Chen C, Li Y, Fu K, Dai J, Hitz EM, Xie H, Liu B, Song J, Yang B. Three-dimensional printed thermal regulation textiles. *ACS nano*. 2017 Nov 28; 11 (11):11513-20
- [16] Pattinson SW, Huber ME, Kim S, Lee J, Grunsfeld S, Roberts R, Dreifus G, Meier C, Liu L, Hogan N, Hart AJ. Additive manufacturing of biomechanically tailored meshes for compliant wearable and implantable devices. *Advanced Functional Materials*. 2019 Aug; 29 (32):1901815. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201901815>
- [17] Wang Y, Li L, Hofmann D, Andrade JE, Daraio C. Structured fabrics with tunable mechanical properties. *Nature*. 2021 Aug 12; 596 (7871):238-43. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03698-7>
- [18] Jiang Y, Cheng M, Shahbazian-Yassar R, Pan Y. Direct ink writing of wearable thermoresponsive supercapacitors with rGO/CNT composite electrodes. *Advanced Materials Technologies*. 2019 Dec;4 (12):1900691. <https://doi.org/10.1002/admt.201900691>
- [19] Zhang M, Zhao M, Jian M, Wang C, Yu A, Yin Z, Liang X, Wang H, Xia K, Liang X, Zhai J. Printable smart pattern for multifunctional energy-management E-textile. *Matter*. 2019 Jul 10;1 (1):168-79.
- [20] Chen S, Huang T, Zuo H, Qian S, Guo Y, Sun L, Lei D, Wu Q, Zhu B, He C, Mo X. A single integrated 3D-printing process customizes elastic and sustainable triboelectric nanogenerators for wearable electronics. *Advanced Functional Materials*. 2018 Nov; 28 (46):1805108. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201805108>
- [21] Chen S, Huang T, Zuo H, Qian S, Guo Y, Sun L, Lei D, Wu Q, Zhu B, He C, Mo X. A single integrated 3D-printing process customizes elastic and sustainable triboelectric nanogenerators for wearable electronics. *Advanced Functional Materials*. 2018 Nov; 28 (46):1805108. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201805108>
- [22] Vanderploeg A, Lee SE, Mamp M. The application of 3D printing technology in the fashion industry. *International Journal of Fashion Design, Technology and Education*. 2017 May 4; 10 (2):170-9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17543266.2016.1223355>
- [23] Chakraborty S, Biswas MC. 3D printing technology of polymer-fiber composites in textile and fashion industry: A potential roadmap of concept to consumer. *Composite Structures*. 2020 Sep 15; 248:112562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.112562>
- [24] Yap YL, Yeong WY. Additive manufacture of fashion and jewellery products: a mini review: This paper provides an insight into the future of 3D printing industries for fashion and jewellery products. *Virtual and Physical Prototyping*. 2014 Jul 3; 9 (3):195-201. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17452759.2014.938993>

- [25] Rahman MM. Applications of the digital technologies in textile and fashion manufacturing industry. *Technium: Romanian Journal of Applied Sciences and Technology*. 2021; 3 (1):114-27. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3777742>
- [26] Korger M, Bergschneider J, Lutz M, Mahltig B, Finsterbusch K, Rabe M. Possible applications of 3D printing technology on textile substrates. *INOP conference series: materials science and engineering 2016 Jul 1* (Vol. 141, No. 1, p. 012011). IOP Publishing
- [27] Beecroft M. 3D printing of weft knitted textile based structures by selective laser sintering of nylon powder. *INOP conference series: Materials science and engineering 2016 Jul 1* (Vol. 137, No. 1, p. 012017). IOP Publishing. 10.1088/1757-899X/137/1/012017
- [28] Zhang M, Wang J, Pan L, Zhang CY. The application of 3D printing technology in the field of clothing. *Shanghai Textile Technology*. 2018; 12, 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.31058/j.ad.2022.53014>
- [29] Ge Q, Li Z, Wang Z, Kowsari K, Zhang W, He X, Zhou J, Fang NX. Projection micro stereolithography based 3D printing and its applications. *International Journal of Extreme Manufacturing*. 2020 Jun 4; 2 (2):022004. 10.1088/2631-7990/ab8d9a
- [30] Şahin K, Turan Bo. Üç Boyutlu Yazıcı Teknolojilerinin Karşılaştırmalı Analizi. *Stratejik ve Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*. 2018 Jun 8;2 (2):97-116. <https://doi.org/10.30692/sisad.441648>
- [31] Huang Y, Bu N, Duan Y, Pan Y, Liu H, Yin Z, Xiong Y. Electrohydrodynamic direct-writing. *Nanoscale*. 2013;5 (24):12007-17. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C3NR04329K>
- [32] Chen Y, Deng Z, Ouyang R, Zheng R, Jiang Z, Bai H, Xue H. 3D printed stretchable smart fibers and textiles for self-powered e-skin. *Nano Energy*. 2021 Jun 1; 84:105866. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2021.105866>
- [33] Wu MJ, Zhi C, Tu L, Wang YZ, Dai Y, Yu LJ, Meng JG, He XY. Cotton-containing printing wires based on the two-dimensional braiding method for three-dimensional printing of clothing. *Textile Research Journal*. 2022 May;92 (9-10):1384-93. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0040517521105920>
- [34] Chatterjee K, Ghosh TK. 3D printing of textiles: potential roadmap to printing with fibers. *Advanced Materials*. 2020 Jan; 32 (4):1902086. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201902086>
- [35] Mohamed OA, Masood SH, Bhowmik JL. Optimization of fused deposition modeling process parameters for dimensional accuracy using I-optimality criterion. *Measurement*. 2016 Mar 1; 81:174-96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2015.12.011>
- [36] Fanglan Z, Kaifa D. Innovative application of 3D printing technology in Fashion design. *InJournal of Physics: Conference Series 2021 Feb 1* (Vol. 1790, No. 1, p. 012030). IOP Publishing. 10.3390/coatings12020267.
- [37] Chen Y, Deng Z, Ouyang R, Zheng R, Jiang Z, Bai H, Xue H. 3D printed stretchable smart fibers and textiles for self-powered e-skin. *Nano Energy*. 2021 Jun 1; 84:105866. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2021.105866>
- [38] Huang Y, Bu N, Duan Y, Pan Y, Liu H, Yin Z, Xiong Y. Electrohydrodynamic direct-writing. *Nanoscale*. 2013;5 (24):12007-17. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C3NR04329K>
- [39] Mohamed OA, Masood SH, Bhowmik JL. Optimization of fused deposition modeling process parameters: a review of current research and future prospects. *Advances in manufacturing*. 2015 Mar; 3:42-53. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40436-014-0097-7>.
- [40] TWI Ltd. What are the Advantages and Disadvantages of 3D Printing? Available online: <https://www.twi-global.com/technicalknowledge/faqs/what-is-3d-printing/pros-and-cons> (accessed on 17 May 2023)
- [41] Park S, Shou W, Makatura L, Matusik W, Fu KK. 3D printing of polymer composites: Materials, processes, and applications. *Matter*. 2022 Jan 5;5 (1):43-76
- [42] 3Dhubs homepage. Will 3D printing replace traditional manufacturing? The advantages of 3D printing. Hubs:A Protolabs company. Available online: <https://www.3dhubs.com/knowledge-base/advantages-3d-printing/> (accessed on 16 May 2023)
- [43] Danit Peleg. Danit Peleg Creates First 3D Printed Fashion Collection. *Big See Fashion Design Award 2021*; Oct 20, 2021. Available online: <https://bigsee.eu/danit-peleg-danit-peleg-3d-danit-peleg-nft-collection-liberty-leading-the-people/> (accessed on 15 May 2023).
- [44] Juliana Neira. Iris van herpen + magnum debut world's first vegan haute couture dress. *Designboom*; July 05, 2022. Available online: <https://www.designboom.com/design/iris-van-herpen-magnum-vegan-dress-07-05-2022/> (accessed on 16 May 2023).
- [45] Sarah Saunders. Dior Showcases Past & Present of its Brand with Nearly 1,500 3D Printed Items. *3D Print.com*; 18, 2022. Available online: <https://3dprint.com/289763/3d-printing-showcases-past-present-of-dior-brand-at-rebranded-flagship-store/> (accessed on 16 May 2023).
- [46] Rosh Ha'ayn. Kornit Digital Introduces Presto MAX. Kornit Digital Ltd.; Oct 20, 2021. Available online: <https://ir.kornit.com/news-releases/news-release-details/kornit-digital-introduces-presto-max-reinventing-design-and> (accessed on 16 May 2023).
- [47] Alexandra P. 3D Printed Fashion: The Top Designs. *3D Natives*; August 4, 2022. Available online: <https://www.3dnatives.com/en/3d-printing-fashion-designs150620174/#> (accessed on 20 May 2023).
- [48] Sarah Saunders. Anouk Wipprecht's 3D Printed Proximity Dresses Are Perfect for Social Distancing. *3D Print.com*; June 2, 2020. Available online: <https://3dprint.com/268227/anouk-wipprecht-3d-printed-proximity-dress-is-perfect-for-social-distancing/> (accessed on 22 May 2023).
- [49] Danielle Matich. Karl Lagerfeld showcases 3d printed Chanel at Paris Fashion Week. *3D Printing Industry*; July 08th 2015. Available online: <https://3dprintingindustry.com/news/karl-lagerfeld-showcases-3d-printed-chanel-fashion-at-paris->

fashion-week-53000/(accessed on 27 May 2023).

[50] Michelle J. Interview with Julia Körner: About 3D printing in design and its myths. 3D Natives; July 16, 2018. Available online: <https://www.3dnatives.com/en/interview-julia-korner160720184/#> (accessed on 11 May 2023).

[51] Jackson O'Connell. 3D Printed Dress: 10 Awesome Projects. Craftcloud; Sep 6, 2020. Available online: <https://all3dp.com/2/3d-printed-fashion-3d-printed-dress/> (accessed on 17 May 2023).